

Supplementary Materials for Hidden processing drivers of thermoelectric performance in tetrahedrites

Catarina Quitério^{1,2,3*}, Kalpna Rajput¹,
Konstantina Iordanidou¹, Vetle Øversjøen¹, Daniel Marchand⁴,
Salah Amedi⁵, Ana Sá⁶, Paulo Luz⁶, Alvise Bianchin⁷,
Marcin Rosinski⁸, Daniela Gomes², Francisco Molina-Lopez³,
Filipe Neves⁶, Patricia Almeida Carvalho^{1,9*}

^{1*}Sustainable Energy Technology, SINTEF Industry, Forskningsveien 1,
Oslo, 0373, Norway.

²CENIMAT|i3N, Department of Materials Science, School of Science
and Technology, NOVA University, Largo da Torre, Caparica, 2829-516,
Portugal.

³Department of Materials Engineering (MTM), KU Leuven,
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44 - bus 2450, Leuven, 3001, Belgium.

⁴Metal Production and Processing, SINTEF Industry, Forskningsveien
1, Oslo, 0373, Norway.

⁵Process Technology, SINTEF Industry, Forskningsveien 1, Oslo, 0373,
Norway.

⁶Materials for Energy Unit, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia,
Estrada do Paço do Lumiar, Ed.C, Lisbon, 1649-038, Portugal.

⁷MBN nanomaterialia srl, via Bortolan, 42, Carbonera, 31050, Italy.

⁸Genicore Sp. z o.o., Wólczyńska, Warsaw, 01-919, Poland.

⁹CeFEMA, Departamento de Engenharia Química, Instituto Superior
Técnico, Av. Rovisco Pais, 1, Lisbon, 1049-001, Portugal.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): catarina.querio@kuleuven.be;
patricia.carvalho@sintef.no;

Contributing authors: kalpna.rajput@sintef.no;
konstantina.iordanidou@sintef.no; vetle.oversjoen@sintef.no;
daniel.marchand@sintef.no; Salah.Amedi@sintef.no; ana.sa@lneg.pt;
paulo.luz@lneg.pt; research@mbn.it; marcin.rosinski@genicore.pl;
daniela.gomes@fct.unl.pt; francisco.molinalopez@kuleuven.be;
filipe.neves@lneg.pt;

Figure S 1: Scatter plots showing the dependence of zT on measurement temperature for tetrahedrites: (a) full dataset and (b) undoped tetrahedrites. Quantile regressions corresponding to the median ($zT_{50\%}$), 75%, and 95% levels are shown with the corresponding quantile-regression equations also presented below the plots. Selected high-performing data are indicated by stars and identified below the plots, with additional details provided in Figure S2 (SI). Panels (c) to (e) show hexabin plots of the full dataset for (c) Seebeck coefficient, (d) electrical conductivity, and (e) thermal conductivity as functions of temperature.

Figure S 2: Peak zT values reported for tetrahedrites produced via mechanochemical synthesis followed by pressure-assisted sintering, with respective measurement temperature [1–6]. Bars sharing the same colour correspond to compositions reported within the same study. These data have not been included in Figures 3 and 4 because the values were not obtained at 350 °C).

Figure S 3: Effect of sintering temperature on TE performance of undoped tetrahedrites. All zT values are measured at 350 °C. Stars represent the highest values.

Figure S 4: Results for the sample subset with relative density $\geq 95\%$, corresponding to 77% of the database. (a) zT as a function of temperature. The 50%, 75%, and 95% quantile regressions are comparable to those of the full dataset in Figure S1 (a). (b) Effect of sintering temperature on zT measured at 350 °C (compare with Figure 4 (b)).

Figure S 5: Diffractograms for $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ (red) and $\text{Cu}_{11}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ (grey) samples. The major phase in both samples is tetrahedrite ($\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$) (ICSD 01-088-0282). The $\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$ sample exhibits a minor amount of famatinite (Cu_3SbS_4) (*) (ICSD 01-071-0555)

Figure S 6: (a) Projected density of states for Cu atoms at the 12d and 12e Wyckoff positions in tetrahedrite, highlighting the distinct contributions of the inequivalent Cu sites to the electronic states. (b) Band-decomposed charge density of the four highest valence bands crossing the Fermi level, visualized in VESTA with an isosurface value of $0.009 \text{ e}/\text{\AA}^3$.

Table S 1: Highest zT values reported in the literature for different tetrahedrite compounds. All zT values were measured (or interpolated) at 350°C .

Composition	Dopant	Substitution	zT @350 °C	Reference
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	-	(undoped)	0.77	Kumar 2017 [7]
$\text{Cu}_{13.5}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}\text{Se}$	Cu	- (excess)	0.85	Yan 2018 [5]
$\text{Cu}_{11.9}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	\square	Cu (deficiency)	0.70	Kwak 2022 [8]
$\text{Cu}_{10.5}\text{Mg}_{1.5}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Mg	Cu	0.51	Levinsky 2019 [9]
$\text{Cu}_{11.9}\text{Al}_{0.1}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Al	Cu	0.55	Tippireddy 2020 [10]
$\text{Cu}_{11.65}\text{Cr}_{0.35}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Cr	Cu	0.85	Kumar 2019 [2]
$\text{Cu}_{11.8}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Mn	Cu	0.34	Kim 2020 [11]
$\text{Cu}_{11.8}\text{Fe}_{0.2}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Fe	Cu	0.61	Kim 2020 [12]
$\text{Cu}_{11.5}\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Co	Cu	0.80	Chetty 2015 [13]
$\text{Cu}_{11}\text{NiSb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Ni	Cu	0.84	Sun 2018 [14]
$\text{Cu}_{11.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Zn	Cu	0.80	Morelli 2020 [15]
$\text{Cu}_{11.7}\text{Ge}_{0.3}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Ge	Cu	0.58	Kosaka 2017 [16]
$\text{Cu}_{11.25}\text{Cd}_{0.75}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Cd	Cu	0.90	Kumar 2019 [2]
$\text{Cu}_{11.6}\text{Sn}_{0.4}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Sn	Cu	0.62	Kosaka 2017 [16]
$\text{Cu}_{11}\text{PbSb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Pb	Cu	0.57	Huang 2018 [17]
$\text{Cu}_{11.7}\text{Gd}_{0.3}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{13}$	Gd	Cu	0.60	Zhu 2021 [18]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{4.1}\text{S}_{13}\text{Se}$	Sb	- (excess)	0.65	Huang 2020 [19]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{S}_{13}$	\square	Sb (deficiency)	0.50	Huang 2020 [19]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{Ge}_{0.2}\text{S}_{13}$	Ge	Sb	0.52	Jeong 2022 [20]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{3.65}\text{Sn}_{0.35}\text{S}_{13}$	Sn	Sb	0.81	Tippireddy 2019 [21]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{Te}_{0.2}\text{S}_{13}$	Te	Sb	0.79	Bouyrie 2015 [22]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_{3.8}\text{Bi}_{0.2}\text{S}_{13}$	Bi	Sb	0.78	Kumar 2017 [7]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{12.6}$	\square	S (deficiency)	0.45	Sun 2017 [23]
$\text{Cu}_{12}\text{Sb}_4\text{S}_{12.8}\text{Se}_{0.2}$	Se	S	0.59	Zhu 2019 [24]

Table S 2:

Mann–Whitney U test results comparing the undoped reference (47 data points) to each doped condition. Two-sided tests were performed at $\alpha = 0.05$ owing to skewed distributions and unequal sample sizes. Effect sizes are reported as the rank-biserial correlation ($r_{rb} = 1 - \frac{2U}{n_{\text{Undoped}} n_{\text{Doped}}}$), and categorized as none ($|r_{rb}| < 0.1$), small ($0.1 \leq |r_{rb}| < 0.3$), medium ($0.3 \leq |r_{rb}| < 0.5$), or large ($|r_{rb}| \geq 0.5$).

Dopant	Substitution	Set size (N)	U	p-value	Effect size (r)	Interpretation
Cu	- (excess)	6	81.0	0.094	0.43	Medium (\uparrow)
\square	Cu (deficiency)	3	34.5	0.147	0.51	Large (\uparrow)
Mg	Cu	3	76.0	0.838	-0.08	None
Al	Cu	4	109.5	0.599	-0.16	Small
Cr	Cu	6	73.5	0.060	0.48	Medium (\uparrow)
Mn	Cu	11	309.0	0.321	-0.20	Small
Fe	Cu	10	344.5	0.022	-0.47	Medium (\downarrow)
Co	Cu	15	245.0	0.078	0.30	Medium (\uparrow)
Ni	Cu	16	254.0	0.055	0.32	Medium (\uparrow)
Zn	Cu	13	297.5	0.893	0.03	None
Ge	Cu	6	107.5	0.354	0.24	Small
Cd	Cu	7	155.5	0.827	0.05	None
Sn	Cu	5	95.5	0.504	0.19	Small
Pb	Cu	6	156.5	0.673	-0.11	Small
Gd	Cu	5	110.0	0.828	0.06	None
Sb	- (excess)	3	58.0	0.624	0.18	Small
\square	Sb (deficiency)	2	51.0	0.859	-0.09	None
Ge	Sb	6	107.5	0.354	0.24	Small
Sn	Sb	8	196.0	0.858	-0.04	None
Te	Sb	16	289.5	0.174	0.23	Small
Bi	Sb	8	134.0	0.201	0.29	Small
\square	S (deficiency)	2	62.0	0.463	-0.32	Medium (\downarrow)
Se	S	11	264.0	0.921	-0.02	None

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